

Role of MgO additive in reaction sintering of bauxite and titania

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Raw bauxite and titania with molar ratio of Al_2O_3 : TiO_2 as 1.2 : 1 were wet milled with varying amount of MgO. The milled powder after drying was pressed into briquettes, which were then sintered at various temperatures from 1400 to 1550°. MgO additive (about 1%) influenced the extent of sintering and quality of the product to the maximum extent.

Gani and Mcpherson¹ used SiO_2 , MgO and ZrO_2 to stabilize and strengthen the aluminium titanate compound. Byrne *et al.*² studied the thermal expansion characteristics and thermal stability of aluminium titanate. They obtained the best stability from a composition containing both MgO and SiO_2 . Wohlfromm *et al.*³ studied microstructural characterisation of aluminium titanate based composite materials. They showed complete disorder in cationic sublattice of Al_2TiO_5 even in presence of Mg. Perera *et al.*⁴ observed final stage sintering of aluminium titanate without and with additives e.g. MgO, Fe_2O_3 and SiO_2 by hot isostatic pressing. A lower porosity and a finer grain size were activated by higher sintering temperature. Djambazov *et al.*⁵ studied stabilization of aluminium titanate. They synthesized Al_2TiO_5 at 1500° incorporating CaF_2 , La_2O_3 , SiO_2 and MgO additives, stabilised ceramic material was produced with MgO additive. Grimes *et al.*⁶ observed defect formation in $\beta\text{-Al}_2\text{TiO}_5$ and its influence on structural stability. They also discussed solution mechanism of MgO and excess TiO_2 in $\beta\text{-Al}_2\text{TiO}_5$. Kim⁷ obtained Al_2TiO_5 with excellent thermal shock resistance and a low thermal expansion coefficient with MgO, SiO_2 , ZrO_2 as additive.

Li *et al.*⁸ studied the effects of various additives on the stability and strength of Al_2TiO_5 . The results showed that moderate amount of fused magnesite powder, SiO_2 powder and ZrO_2 can enhance the stability and strength to different extents. Barrios de Arenas *et al.*⁹ studied the effect of 3 wt% V_2O_5 , Na_2O , CaO and FeTiO_3 on the stabilization of Al_2TiO_5 . In the present investigation, the effect of MgO as an additive on the sintering of raw bauxite and titania mixture for the formation of aluminium titanate was studied.

Results and discussion

The molar ratio of Al_2O_3 and TiO_2 was kept at 1.2 : 1. The specific surface area of the raw material powders was $125 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, which was sufficient enough for better compaction without any binder. The DTA curves of bauxite show an endothermic peak at 300° and that of titania reveals non-existence of either endothermic or exothermic peak. The shrinkage of the compacts during sintering was mainly due to expulsion of the residual water from the mixture and the products crystallize from the amorphous part where the temperature range is 1400–1550°. The increase of firing shrinkage might be due to grain growth of the respective crystalline phases. At a particular temperature, with the increase of the additive, the extent of shrinkage also increases.

Apparent porosity values of the sintered compacts decreased from Batch I to Batch IV at a particular temperature of firing. But the decrease of apparent porosity at 1500° is much higher compared to that at 1550°. This might be due to higher sintering and densification of the samples at 1500°. The above confirmed that with the increase in temperature of firing and MgO content, sintering and/or coarsening due to grain growth led to reduction in apparent porosity. Gradual increase of bulk density with temperature indicates respective relation of sinterability with temperature. This was common to all the batches although the magnitude was different. From an analysis of the true density values it is noted that upto 1500°, the values for Batch I and Batch II increased slowly but for Batch III and Batch IV, it increased to a considerable extent. But from 1500 to 1550°, the true density values increased suddenly in case of all the batches, which might be due to maximum development of aluminium titanate phases and densification at

1550°. It can be concluded that as the density increase occurred in steps, it was a clear indication of reaction sintering process and formation of aluminium titanate and densification occurred separately.

All the sintered products were subjected to thermal spalling i.e. heating at 800° for 10 min and then quenched in air for 10 min. It is observed that all the samples of Batches I, II, III and IV fired at 1400, 1500 and 1550° could withstand 40 cycles without any visible cracks due to air quenching. The above spalling resistances might be due to the formation of low expansion titanate phase along with sharp grain boundaries with minimum glassy phase. It is seen that the refractory material developed after firing at 1500 and 1550° with 1% MgO content (Batch II) had very high compressive strength. It is noted that with increase in MgO content beyond 1%, there is generally a trend of decrease in compressive strength. The above reduction might be due to formation of glassy phases.

From XRD diagrams of the samples of Batches I, II, III and IV – all fired at 1550°, aluminium titanate was found to

Fig. 1(a). SEM photograph of Sample I fired at 1550°.

be the major phase, corundum was found as minor phase in all the above fired samples although mullite was also found as minor phase only in Batches I and II. The SEM analysis (Figs. 1(a, b)) of Batch I sample indicates distribution of titanate phase along with corundum with sharp grain boundary. With the introduction of MgO, the microstructure changed significantly with some needle shaped mullite crystals formed by secondary crystallization. The mi-

crostructure initially contains some sub-rounded particles, but with 5% MgO in Batch IV, there is excessive growth, which exhibited some transangular cracks in the microstructure. The growth disappeared with increase in MgO content.

Conclusion :

Low expansion aluminium titanate can be produced through reaction sintering of bauxite and titania in the temperature 1400–1550°. With the incorporation of MgO, the matrix become strengthened upto an optimum addition of 1% MgO, above which it imparted some deleterious effect in microstructure. This may be due to formation of glassy phases.

Fig. 1(b). SEM photograph of Sample II fired at 1550°.

Table 1. Composition of batches (g)

Batch no.	Magnesium carbonate	Bauxite	TiO ₂
I	0.00	223.82	76.18
II	6.49	221.54	75.46
III	19.48	217.11	73.89
IV	32.47	212.63	72.37

Experimental

Raw bauxite (Lohardaga), TiO₂ (A.R., 98.92%), MgCO₃ (A.R., 46.19% MgO and 53.81% LOI) were used as the starting material for the synthesis of aluminium titanate. The bauxite sample was analysed and the results are SiO₂–1.81%, Al₂O₃–64.55%, Fe₂O₃–2.60%, TiO₂–1.79%, CaO–2.06% and LOI–27.18%. Table 1 indicates composition of various batches. Required amount of raw bauxite and tita-

nia were taken in the molar ratio of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{TiO}_2$ as 1.2 : 1. MgCO_3 was added in various amounts. DTA analysis of raw bauxite and titania was carried out with Netzsch STA-409 analyser. Infrared spectra (KBr) was carried out with a Nicole FTIR spectrophotometer. Briquettes of samples were fabricated at a pressure of 2000 kg/cm^2 in a hydraulic press without any extra binder. The briquettes were sintered at 1400 , 1500 and 1550° respectively in an electrically heated muffle furnace with 2 h of soaking period. The heating rate of the briquettes was $10^\circ/\text{min}$ upto 1000° and then $5^\circ/\text{min}$ to the final temperature of heat treatment. X-Ray diffraction was recorded on a Philips PW-1730 diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. SEM photographs were taken by S-530 (Hitachi, Japan) Scanning Electron Microscope.

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